

GAMIFICATION IS AN INNOVATIVE FIELD OF STUDY

Kuanyshbaeva Gulnara Bakhitzhanovna,
teacher, Khoja Ahmed Yasawi International
Kazakh-Turkish University
Aldashbek Janel, 1nd-year student
Khoja Ahmed Yasawi International
Kazakh-Turkish University

Abstract: Playing is a free and exciting activity that is important for a person's physical and mental well-being, regardless of their age. For children, play is the main means of development through which they explore the world, learn social skills and develop creative abilities. The game is also important for adults: it helps to reduce stress, develop concentration and strengthen social ties. And the way game elements are incorporated into the educational process is called gamification. This method does not simply turn learning into a game, but rather applies attractive and stimulating game mechanisms to learning objectives. This helps students to increase interest in lessons, strengthen motivation, and learn knowledge more easily and effectively. In this article, games and contests explore the interaction, collaboration, and teamwork skills of students with each other.

Keywords: game, gamification, curiosity, motivation, development, creativity, skills, mission, rating, evaluation.

Introduction

Playing is a free and exciting activity that is important for a person's physical and mental well-being, regardless of their age. For children, play is the main means of development through which they explore the world, learn social skills and develop creative abilities. The game is also important for adults: it helps to reduce stress, develop concentration and strengthen social ties. And the way game elements are incorporated into the educational process is called gamification.

Results and discussion. Gamification is the introduction of game elements into the educational process. This method does not simply turn learning into a game, but rather applies attractive and stimulating game mechanisms to learning objectives. This helps students to increase interest in lessons, strengthen motivation, and learn knowledge more easily and effectively.

Gamification is based on the use of basic game elements that affect human psychology.:

1. Points system: Students earn points for completing a task, answering correctly, or actively participating in a lesson. This will encourage them to see their progress and try to achieve the goal.
2. Ratings or Leaderboards: Allows you to compare student scores. This creates a competitive spirit and encourages students to achieve high results.
3. Badges and Awards: the presentation of vertical awards or badges for achieving a certain success. For example, signs such as "excellent student", "with a large vocabulary" or "mathematical genius" increase a student's self-esteem.
4. Levels and Missions: dividing the learning process by difficulty levels. As each level progresses, the student progresses to the next, more difficult level. This turns learning into an exciting journey towards achieving one goal.
5. Storytelling: link the curriculum to an interesting storyline or storyline. For example, topics such as "history researchers" or "the mathematical mission of Astronauts" develop the student's imagination and increase his interest in reading.

The scoring system is one of the most common and basic elements of gamification. It is a system that allows you to quantify student activity, progress, and achievements. This method makes the learning process more exciting and increases the motivation of students to study.

The logic of the points system is very simple: students earn points for performing various actions. They are:

1. for the correct answer: for the correct answer during the lesson or test tasks.
2. For being active: for actively participating in a class, asking questions, or participating in a discussion.
3. for timely completion of homework: for completing a given task on time.
4. for solving a complex problem: for completing additional complex tasks and finding creative solutions.

The earned points can then be used for various purposes. For example, they determine a place on rating boards or allow you to receive awards and badges.

Advantages of the points system in education:

1. Increases motivation: students can clearly see their achievements by gaining points. This encourages them to move forward and gain new knowledge.
2. Instant feedback: The points system allows the teacher to receive timely information about the students' level of knowledge and attendance activity. Students also monitor their performance.
3. Makes the learning process fun: Scoring is part of the game. This turns learning into an exciting competition rather than just completing tasks.

4. Develops the spirit of competition: displaying places on the rating board using points creates healthy competition between students.

5. Additional reward opportunity: Students can receive additional "prizes" for earned points, such as permission to leave the classroom a few minutes earlier or an additional point.

Materials and methods. Leaderboards are one of the most effective elements of gamification. It is a mechanism that demonstrates students' activity and achievements, encouraging them to compare each other and compete healthily. These boards show the best performers or the participants who scored the most points, just like in games.

Advantages of ratings in education

Increases motivation

- Students tend to see their names on the rating board, especially at a higher place. This encourages them to keep trying and improve their results.

Healthy competition

- Leaderboards create a spirit of friendly rivalry between students. This teaches them not only to strive for victory, but also to respect others and learn from them.

Demonstration of achievements

- This system shows students' achievements to the general public. When students' achievements are evaluated and recognized, their self-esteem increases.

An additional incentive

- Students who take the first place in the ranking or score the most points may be awarded additional awards. For example, badges, special certificates of honor, or gifts.

How does the leaderboard work? This system ranks students based on the scores they have scored, the levels they have completed, or the assignments they have completed. It usually comes in two types:

1. Overall Rating: This board displays the results of all participants. The student can compare his position with others and see how he is moving forward.
2. Small group ranking: In some cases, students are divided into small groups and ranked only within this group. This can limit competition and help avoid pressure on individual students.

3. Students who take the first place in the ranking or score the most points may be awarded additional awards. For example, badges, special certificates of honor, or gifts.

The results of the study. Badges and Awards: recognition and encouragement of achievements.

Awards and badges are one of the most visual and emotional elements of gamification. These are virtual or physical signals that mean that the student has achieved a certain success or achieved a certain goal. This method can increase students' motivation and help them recognize their work.

How do awards and badges work? The reward system is closely related to the scoring system. When students score a certain number of points or perform a certain action, they are given a badge. For example: for direct achievements:

You can arrange such awards as "book student" — for reading five books in a month, "master of mathematics" — for the faultless completion of all mathematical tasks.

The award for efforts includes certificates: "hardworking" — for trying to complete the most difficult tasks, "assistant" — for helping a classmate solve a difficult task.

Various certificates can be awarded for participation: "Active" — for constant participation in the lesson, for questions, "Time manager" — for timely completion of all homework. Badges are often displayed in the profile or on a separate page, which allows students to be proud of their achievements.

The educational benefits of awards and badges motivate students, and badges are a real, visible achievement for a student that they motivate to keep learning in order to earn the next badge. Each icon requires a specific goal to be achieved. This helps students break down the learning process into smaller and more achievable goals.

Increases self-esteem: Socially recognized achievements increase a student's self-confidence, and each badge shows that his knowledge and work are valued. Rewards and badges also change the learning process from "completing tasks" to "collecting achievements." This makes learning more fun. By creating a sense of community among students, students have the opportunity to collect badges together or see and support each other's achievements.

Levels and Missions are one of the most interesting and effective elements of gamification in education. This system breaks down the learning process into smaller, more feasible parts and gives the student a sense of progress. Each level represents a specific stage of knowledge, and the mission reflects a specific set of tasks that must be completed at this stage.

How do the levels and missions work? This method builds a training program in the same way as the plot of the game. Levels: The training material is grouped by difficulty level. After a student successfully completes one level, they move on to the next, more difficult level. For example,

This helps the student to gradually and systematically assimilate knowledge. Within each level there will be certain missions that the student must complete. For example:

Mission 1: Memorizing 10 new words.

Mission 2: He uses words to make 5 sentences.

Mission 3: Reading compound sentences to the teacher.

Only after completing these missions does the student have the opportunity to move on to the next level.

Educational benefits of levels and missions

1. Setting a clear goal: Students know that the goal they are facing is clear. For example, instead of the general goal of "learning how to compose a complex sentence," a specific goal is set to "complete Level 5."

" 2. A sense of progress: students clearly see their achievements as they progress through each level. This sense of accomplishment motivates them to move forward.

3. Make learning fun: The learning process turns from "boring lessons" into "exciting missions." Students perceive learning as a competition on the way to achieving a goal, just like in any game.

4. Simplify complex tasks: By breaking complex topics into multiple missions, it will be easier for the student to master them. For example, instead of "studying complex functions", you can sort it into "mission 1: Studying the definition of a function", "mission 2: plotting".

The system of levels and missions makes learning purposeful and exciting. This will increase the motivation of students to learn and allow them to evaluate each of their achievements.

Turning learning into an exciting journey Storytelling is one of the most creative and fascinating elements of gamification in education. This method is based on turning the learning process into an interesting story or story, rather than just memorizing facts and formulas. Students, with the help of a teacher, play the role of one character and perform various tasks to achieve his goals.

How does the storyline work? To use this method, the teacher comes up with an interesting story for the lesson or course. For example: In the history lesson, the storyline is as follows: students become a group of "time travelers" and set off to solve the mysteries of the past. Each topic (for example, "Ancient Egypt") is a separate mission.

Students study hieroglyphs (reading text), collect information about the pharaohs (research), and learn how to solve historical problems (mathematical calculations) in order to uncover the mystery of pyramid construction. Thus, each task acquires meaning and increases the student's interest.

Speaking about the advantages of a storyline in education to increase interest, students perceive education as an exciting adventure, not as a compulsory activity. This will increase their motivation to study.

An emotional connection: The storyline helps the student to establish an emotional connection with the material. When they overcome difficulties and win together with the character, the learning material becomes more important to them.

1. Memorizing knowledge: The human brain remembers events better than facts. The eventful learning material stays in the student's memory longer.

2. The development of creativity: Participation in the storyline develops the student's creative and critical abilities. They plan the next step in history and learn how to solve problems creatively.

3. Collaboration: Group missions and events allow students to collaborate with each other and work towards a common goal.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the advantages of gamification in education are to increase students' motivation, motivate them to work actively without getting tired of classes, and develop an interest in learning. Gamification also makes learning more engaging, and explaining complex topics in a playful way helps to keep the student's attention for a longer period of time.

Through repetitive tasks or missions during the game, students consciously repeat their knowledge and memorize it. Team games and competitions develop students' ability to communicate, collaborate and work in a team. The fear of making a

mistake or losing the game decreases. Students will be ready to try new ideas and try again without fear of failure. Students create a safe environment by developing communication skills.

References:

1. Yu-kai Chou "Actionable Gamification: Beyond Points, Badges, and Leaderboards" ("Real gamification: How to make motivation and design work" - orysshha audarmasy), Moscow 2011
2. Kevin Werbach, Dan Hunter "For the Win: How Game Thinking Can Revolutionize Your Business" ("Gamification. How to make the mechanisms of games work in business" - orysshha audarmasy), St. Petersburg, 2015
3. Anton Stupakov, Anna Chernysheva "Gamification in business: How to turn routine into a game", Moscow 2021
4. Karl M. Kapp, "The Gamification of Learning and Instruction" (orysshha audarmasy), Tallinn, 2018